

Use of distance-based topological indices for the estimation of ^{13}C NMR shifts : A case of benzene derivatives^ψ

Mona Jaiswal and Padmakar Khadikar*

Research Division, Laxmi Fumigation & Pest Control (P), 3, Khatipura, Indore-452 007, India

E-mail : pvkhadikar@rediffmail.com, tomona@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-731-2701170

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A pool of distance-based topological indices has been used for the estimation of ^{13}C NMR shifts in benzene derivatives. The regression analysis of the data has shown that Wiener (W)-, Szeged (Sz)-, PI (Padmakar-Ivan)- and first-order molecular connectivity ($^1\chi$)- indices gave more or less similar results, $^1\chi$ gave slightly better results. The use of other indices were less significant.

In continuation of our work on the use of topological indices for the estimation prediction of ^{13}C NMR shifts¹, we now discuss the use of distance-based topological indices for modeling, monitoring, and estimating ^{13}C NMR shifts in benzene derivatives.

For estimating/predicting the aforementioned ^{13}C NMR shifts we have used Wiener (W)-, Szeged (Sz)-, (Padmakar-Ivan) PI-, Randic connectivity ($^0\chi$, $^1\chi$, $^2\chi$)- and Kier and Hall valence connectivity ($^0\chi^v$, $^1\chi^v$, $^2\chi^v$)-indices². The estimation/prediction of ^{13}C NMR shift is made by correlation analysis using the method of least squares³.

The calculation of aforementioned distance-based topological indices is made using the corresponding molecular graph which is obtain by suppression of all the hydrogen atoms of the molecular structure. The method of calculation of these indices are already described in the literature⁴.

Results and discussion

The ^{13}C NMR chemical shift data used here are relative to benzene. These adopted data are given in Table 1. The distance-based topological indices (W, Sz, PI, χ , $^1\chi$, $^2\chi$, $^0\chi^v$, $^1\chi^v$ and $^2\chi^v$) calculated for the above mentioned benzene derivatives are recorded in Table 2. The data presented in Tables 1 and 2 shows that degeneracy is present in the topological indices. This is due to the fact that they belongs either to first generation (W, Sz, PI) or to second generation (χ , $^1\chi$, $^2\chi$, $^0\chi^v$, $^1\chi^v$, $^2\chi^v$) topological indices⁵. Such indices inspite of their observed degeneracy can be used successfully in QSPR/QSAR studies. The preliminary regression procedure has indicated that compounds 9 and 10 are outli-

Table 1. Benzene derivatives. ^{13}C NMR shifts and W, Sz, PI indices

Sl. no.	R	^{13}C (obs)	W	Sz	PI
1.	F	4.4	42	78	36
2.	Cl	2.0	42	78	36
3.	Br	1.0	42	78	36
4.	I	0.4	42	78	36
5.	Me	2.8	42	78	36
6.	OMe	8.1	64	109	50
7.	NH ₂	9.5	42	78	36
8.	NMe ₂	11.8	88	142	66
9.	CHO	-6.0	64	109	50
10.	COMe	-4.2	88	142	66
11.	NO ₂	-6.0	88	142	66
12.	H	0.0	27	54	24

Table 2. Molecular connectivity indices ($^0\chi$, $^1\chi$, $^2\chi$, $^0\chi^v$, $^1\chi^v$ and $^2\chi^v$) calculated for the benzene derivatives recorded in Table 1

Sl. no.	$^0\chi$	$^1\chi$	$^2\chi$	$^0\chi^v$	$^1\chi^v$	$^2\chi^v$
1.	5.1129	3.3938	2.7432	3.3868	1.9107	1.0774
2.	5.1129	3.3938	2.7432	3.7647	2.0997	1.2956
3.	5.1129	3.3938	2.7432	3.7647	2.0997	1.2956
4.	5.1129	3.3938	2.7432	3.7647	2.0997	1.2956
5.	5.1129	3.3938	2.7432	4.3868	2.4107	1.6547
6.	5.8200	3.9319	2.9123	4.7950	2.5231	1.5172
7.	5.1129	3.3938	2.7432	3.9641	2.1994	1.4107
8.	6.6902	4.3045	3.6421	5.8340	3.0287	2.2300
9.	5.8200	3.9319	2.9123	4.3723	2.4351	1.5285
10.	6.6902	4.3045	3.6421	5.2950	2.8648	1.9222
11.	6.6902	4.3045	3.6421	4.6505	2.4994	1.5927
12.	4.2426	3.0000	2.1213	3.4641	2.0000	1.1547

^ψDedicated to Navin Jain on the eve of his 29th birthday.

ers. They are, therefore, deleted for the further regression analysis.

We have first attempted one variable regressions using each of 9 parameters are given in Table 3. All of them will, therefore, be mono-parametric regression models. The data presented in Table 3 shows that the attempted mono-parametric regressions confined to the following general expression :

$$^{13}\text{C NMR shift} = A - BX \quad (1)$$

where A is the intercept and B is the slope; while X stands for the topological index used (W , Sz , PI , ${}^0\chi$, ${}^1\chi$, ${}^2\chi$, ${}^0\chi^v$, ${}^1\chi^v$ or ${}^2\chi^v$).

Table 3. Regression parameters and quality of estimation/prediction of ^{13}C nmr shift ($^{13}\text{C} = A + BX$)

Sl. no.	Toological index used	A	B	Se	r	Q
1.	W	-4.8068	0.1932	2.8260	0.7915	0.2801
2.	Sz	-7.2505	0.1362	2.8190	0.7927	0.2812
3.	PI	-6.9766	0.2887	2.8232	0.7920	0.2805
4.	${}^0\chi$	-22.5627	5.1247	2.8575	0.7802	0.2762
5.	${}^1\chi$	-27.3469	9.0547	2.8124	0.7938	0.2823
6.	${}^2\chi$	-18.7903	8.3196	3.0830	0.7453	0.2418
7.	${}^0\chi^v$	-12.8952	4.2036	3.0300	0.7555	0.2493
8.	${}^1\chi^v$	-16.5148	9.2596	3.1160	0.7389	0.2371
9.	${}^2\chi^v$	-8.0936	5.0121	3.3202	0.6901	0.2078

A persual of Table 3 shows that out of the nine mono-parametric regression, the best model is the one involving ${}^1\chi$ index :

$$^{13}\text{C NMR shifts} = -27.3469 (\pm 9.43) + 9.0547 (\pm 2.6222) {}^1\chi \quad (2)$$

$n = 12$, $Se = 2.8124$, $r = 0.7938$, $Q = 0.2823$

The topological index ${}^1\chi$ involved in the above eq. (2) conveys information about the number of atoms and first-order branching in molecule and these parameters are responsible for the exhibition of ^{13}C NMR shift in the present set of compounds.

The statistics for the monoparametric regression involving ${}^1\chi^v$ is quite poor. Thus, the degree of unsaturation and the presence of heteroatoms has lesser effect in the exhibition of ^{13}C NMR shift. Same is true for the present case benzene derivatives also.

The data present in Table 3 also shows that monoparametric regressions involving W , Sz and PI are more or less of similar quality, Sz index giving slightly better results than

both W and PI . This is obvious as Sz is applicable to cyclic graphs only. However, all the compounds under present study contain benzene ring with substitutions on it.

For investigating relative prediction power of the regression models we have calculated Pogliani Q quality factor⁶. This is defined as the ratio of correlation coefficient (r) to the standard error of estimation Se i.e. $Q = r/Se$. These Q factors are also given in Table 3; showing that the regression model containing ${}^1\chi$ has the highest predictive power. Based on the Q values we have the following sequence of predictive potential of the monoparametric regression models :

$${}^1\chi > Sz > PI > W > {}^0\chi > {}^0\chi^v > {}^2\chi > {}^1\chi^v > {}^2\chi^v \quad (3)$$

Conclusions :

From the results and discussion made above we conclude that the distance-based topological indices can be successfully used in monitoring, modeling, and estimating chemical shifts in the NMR spectra. Also, that if the set of compounds used for such study contains a cyclic (aromatic ring) then Sz or PI indices will be better. Effect of side chain on the NMR chemical shifts can be accounted using W index.

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References

1. P. V. Khadikar, A. V. Bajaj and D. Mandloi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 2065; P. V. Khadikar, S. Pathre and A. Shrivastava, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **12**, 2673; P. V. Khadikar, D. Mandloi and A. V. Bajaj, *Oxid. Commun.* (in press).
2. H. Wiener, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 17; I. Gutman, *Graph Theory Notes, New York*, 1994, **27**, 9; P. V. Khadikar, N. V. Deshpande, P. P. Kale, A. Dobrynin, I. Gutman and G. Domotor, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 1995, **35**, 547; P. V. Khadikar, S. Karmarkar and V. K. Agrawal, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 2001, **41**, 934; P. V. Khadikar, P. P. Kale, N. V. Deshpande, S. Karmarkar and V. K. Agrawal, *J. Math. Chem.*, 2001, **29**, 134; P. V. Khadikar, S. Karmarkar and R. G. Varma, *Acta Chem. Slov.*, 2002, **49**, 755; M. Randic, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 6609; *J. Mol. Graph Model*, 2001, **20**, 19; L. B. Kier and L. H. Hall, "Molecular Connectivity in Chemistry and Drug Research", Academic Press, New York, 1976; "Molecular Connectivity in Structure-Activity Analysis", Wiley, New York, 1986.
3. S. Chatterjee, A. Hadi and B. Price, "Regression Analysis by Examples", 3rd ed., Wiley, New York, 2000.
4. S. Singh, S. Joshi, S. Shrivastava and P. V. Khadikar, *Indian J.*

Note

- Sci. Res.*, 2002, **61**, 961; V. K. Agrawal S. Karmarkar, P. V. Khadikar, S. Shrivastava and I. Lukovits, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 1426; P. V. Khadikar, I. Lukovits, V. K. Agrawal, S. Shrivastava, M. Jaiswal, I. Gutman and A. Shrivastava, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 1436.
5. A. T. Balaban, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 1992, **32**, 23.
 6. L. Pogliani, *Amino Acids*, 1994, **6**, 141; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1996, **100**, 18065.